

Research Article

“PANTAS AKAUN” Accounting Game

Norlida Mahussin^{1,*}, Muhammad Zaim Razak²

¹ Risk and Analytics Research Group, Financial Mathematics Programme, Faculty of Science and Technology, Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia; norlida@usim.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6293-1554

² Risk and Analytics Research Group, Financial Mathematics Programme, Faculty of Science and Technology, Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia; mzaim.razak@usim.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0094-096X

* Correspondence: norlida@usim.edu.my; 06-7988778.

Abstract: Many non-accounting students find it difficult to understand the foundational rules of bookkeeping, especially when they have no prior exposure. This leads to reduced focus and participation during accounting lessons. To address this issue, we developed “PANTAS AKAUN,” an interactive and fast-paced card game inspired by the classic ‘Snap Card’ game. The game is designed to teach students how to correctly apply debit and credit rules across five main accounts: Assets, Liabilities, Equity, Revenue, and Expenses. Players compete by identifying matching debit-credit pairs in response to given business transactions and recording them in an Excel spreadsheet. This dual-format approach—traditional cards and digital input—reinforces learning and encourages collaborative teamwork. Designed for tutorial use, the game aligns with weekly accounting topics, promoting active engagement and deeper understanding. Preliminary observations indicate that students playing the game exhibit stronger grasp of the subject and greater motivation. Given its ease of use and adaptability, PANTAS AKAUN holds promise as a scalable educational tool and has potential for broader commercialization.

Keywords: Gamification; Accounting Education; Collaborative Learning

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

The core of accounting education is built upon the principles of bookkeeping, particularly the double-entry system, which is governed by the fundamental accounting equation: **Assets = Liabilities + Capital**. This system requires that every financial transaction be recorded in at least two accounts, with equal debit and credit entries to maintain balance (Waygandt et al., 2015). Mastery of this concept is essential for students to accurately record and interpret financial data. However, many students, especially those without prior exposure to accounting struggle to determine the correct application of debit and credit entries. This situation leads to confusion and a lack of confidence in their understanding of financial accounting.

This challenge is particularly evident at Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia (USIM), where financial accounting is a compulsory course for students enrolled in the Financial Mathematics (FM) and Actuarial Science and Risk Management (ASRM) undergraduate programs. Most of these students have not studied accounting during their secondary or foundation education, making it difficult for them to grasp the foundational concepts of bookkeeping. The course is delivered through a blended learning approach, combining online and face-to-face sessions. Typically, tutorial questions are distributed a week in advance, and students are encouraged to engage in group discussions before presenting their answers during in-person tutorials. However, this method often results in uneven

participation, with some students relying on peers for answers rather than developing their own understanding.

To address these pedagogical limitations, gamification has emerged as a promising instructional strategy. Gamification involves the integration of game design elements into non-game educational contexts to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes (Almuntsr et al., 2024; Lompoliu, 2020). Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of gamified tools in accounting education. For instance, De Oliveira Durso et al. (2020) implemented business simulation games in Brazilian universities to help students prepare financial statements based on real-world scenarios. In Malaysia, the Smart Costing Game has been used to teach cost classification and pricing strategies (Abdul Razak et al., 2019), while in Indonesia, mobile applications have been developed to simulate financial accounting processes using various business contexts (Lompoliu, 2020). Additionally, Selamat and Ngalim (2022) introduced a board game to help first-year students practice journal entries and improve their accuracy in recording transactions.

Building on these innovations, this study introduces **PANTAS AKAUN**, a gamified tutorial tool designed to support students in mastering the fundamentals of bookkeeping. Inspired by the traditional “Snap Card” game popular in the 1980s and 1990s, **PANTAS AKAUN** challenges students to match debit and credit entries for specific business transactions. The game is designed to reinforce weekly accounting concepts through active participation during tutorial sessions, promoting both individual understanding and collaborative learning.

What distinguishes **PANTAS AKAUN** is its creative use of color-coded cards to represent different types of accounts: assets, liabilities, revenues, expenses, and capital accounts. In addition, there is a digital component where students record transactions in an Excel spreadsheet. This hybrid approach blends traditional gameplay with digital tools, transforming conventional instructor-led tutorials into interactive, student-centered learning experiences. The game not only aims to make accounting more accessible and engaging but also seeks to foster deeper conceptual understanding through repeated practice and peer collaboration.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The development of the **PANTAS AKAUN** game followed an iterative design approach, emphasizing simplicity and interactivity to enhance student engagement (Almuntsr et al., 2024). The game involves four key roles: a referee who selects and announces the transaction, two players who compete to match the correct debit and credit entries, and a recorder responsible for updating the journal entries in an Excel spreadsheet.

The gameplay unfolds in six structured steps. In Step 1, the referee draws a transaction card, which includes a partial journal entry—typically the debit side. In Step 2, each player receives an equal stack of face-down cards containing various debit and credit entries related to different business transactions. During Step 3, players take turns flipping their cards. In Step 4, the first player to correctly identify and snap the matching credit entry to complete the journal earns a point, while an incorrect match results in a point deduction. Step 5 involves the recorder entering the completed transaction into the Excel journal. This process continues until all transactions are matched, and the player with the highest score is declared the winner.

The game materials include color-coded paper cards, each representing a different category of accounts: green for assets, red for liabilities, pink for revenues, yellow for expenses, and blue for capital. Transaction prompts are printed on black cards. An Excel spreadsheet is used alongside the physical

cards to record the completed journal entries once a correct debit-credit match is determined by a player.

3. FINDINGS

The introduction of PANTAS AKAUN has shown promising outcomes in enhancing students' understanding of fundamental accounting principles, particularly among those with no prior exposure to the subject. The game provides a structured yet engaging environment where students interact with various business transactions through repeated gameplay. This process helps reinforce the double-entry bookkeeping system, enabling students to better comprehend the relationship between debit and credit entries across different account types, such as assets, liabilities, revenues, and expenses (Selamat & Ngalim, 2022).

By aligning gameplay with the gradual introduction of accounting concepts in lectures, students are able to build familiarity with journal entries over time. The repetitive nature of the game supports memory retention, allowing students to recall and apply accounting concepts more effectively (Almunsr et al., 2024). Furthermore, the game's design encourages active participation, which has been linked to improved academic performance in gamified learning environments (Beatson et al., 2020; Malaquias et al., 2018).

4. DISCUSSION

The findings suggest that gamification, as implemented through PANTAS AKAUN, can serve as a valuable supplement to traditional accounting instruction. The game not only simplifies complex accounting concepts but also fosters intrinsic motivation among students. Unlike extrinsic motivators such as grades or rewards, intrinsic motivation is driven by interest and enjoyment that has been shown to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes (Ayuniar & Fauzan, 2024; Shah, 2017).

PANTAS AKAUN also aligns with Nicholson's (2015) framework of meaningful gamification, where students are given autonomy to engage with the game based on their current level of understanding. The opportunity to make mistakes within a safe, structured environment encourages exploration and deeper learning. Additionally, the collaborative nature of the game promotes peer learning and interdependence, as students rotate roles and support one another throughout the gameplay (Opdecam & Everaert, 2018).

Importantly, the game is designed to be accessible and adaptable. Although it was developed within the context of USIM's undergraduate students, its simplicity and clarity make it suitable for a wide range of learners, from high school students to adult learners in accounting. As such, PANTAS AKAUN holds potential as a scalable educational tool that can be integrated into various levels of accounting education.

5. CONCLUSION

The development and implementation of PANTAS AKAUN demonstrate the potential of gamification as an effective pedagogical tool in accounting education, particularly for students without prior exposure to the subject. By integrating traditional card gameplay with digital tools, the game fosters active participation, collaborative learning, and improved conceptual understanding of double-

entry bookkeeping. The structured yet engaging format allows students to internalize accounting principles through repeated practice and peer interaction. Given its simplicity and adaptability, PANTAS AKAUN offers an innovative approach to supplement traditional accounting instruction across various educational levels.

Acknowledgments: The authors thank Faculty of Science and Technology (FST), Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia (USIM) for their support in the development and classroom implementation of PANTAS AKAUN.

References

- Abdul Razak, R., Kasim, E. S., & Daud, D. (2019). Smart costing kit: Game based learning for cost and management accounting. *Journal Academic Journal*, 15, 1–10.
https://upppp.uitm.edu.my/images/doc/ESTEEM_pdf_format/vol15dec/dec01.pdf
- Almuntsr, Nowara. M., Muhamad, H. B., San, O. T., & Shah, S. M. (2024). Using gamification in accounting education: A systematic literature review (2017 – 2023). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v14-i2/20887>
- Ayuniar, S., & Fauzan, S. (2024). Village-Card: Village Accounting Educational Game. *Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan Ekonomi (JIPE)*, 14(1), 111. <https://doi.org/10.24036/011289930>
- Beatson, N., Gabriel, C. A., Howell, A., Scott, S., van der Meer, J., & Wood, L. C. (2020). Just opt in: How choosing to engage with technology impacts business students' academic performance. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2019.100641>
- De Oliveira Durso, S., Reginato, L., & Cornacchione, E. (2020). Gamification in accounting and students' skillset. *Advances in Scientific and Applied Accounting*, January, 079–100. <https://doi.org/10.14392/asaa.2019120305>
- Lompoliu, E. M. (2020). CREBIT: A gamification of Double Entry Accounting System based on Android application. *CogITo Smart Journal*, 6(1), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.31154/cogito.v6i1.235.107-116>
- Malaquias, R. F., Malaquias, F. F. de O., M Borges Junior, D., & Zambra, P. (2018). The use of a serious game and academic performance of undergraduate accounting students: An empirical analysis. In *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*.
- Nicholson, S. (2015). A recipe for meaningful gamification. In L. Wood & T. Reiners (Eds.), *Gamification in Education and Business* (pp. 1–20). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10208-5_1
- Opdecam, E., & Everaert, P. (2018). Seven disagreements about cooperative learning. *Accounting Education*, 27(3), 223–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2018.1477056>
- Selamat, A. I., & Ngalm, S. M. (2022). Putra Salamanis board game: the game of bookkeeping for fundamental financial accounting learning. *Accounting Education*, 31(5), 596–614.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2021.2015408>
- Shah, K. A. (2017). Game-based accounting learning: the impact of games in learning introductory accounting. *International Journal of Information Systems in the Service Sector*, 9(4), 21–29.
- Waygandt, J., Kimmel, P., & Kieso, D. (2015). *Accounting Principles* (11th ed.). Wiley.